

Supplementary material for:

The relationship between player tracking data and individual risk factors in online sports bettors: an explorative study

Wirkus, T.^{1*}, Czernecka, R.^{1,2}, Bühringer, G.^{1,2} & Kräplin, A.¹

¹Technische Universität Dresden, Dresden, Germany

²IFT Prävention und betriebliche Gesundheitsförderung GmbH, München, Germany

*Corresponding author: Theresa Wirkus

Theresa.wirkus@tu-dresden.de

[ORCID: 0000-0003-3340-4274](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3340-4274)

Institut für Klinische Psychologie und Psychotherapie

Technische Universität Dresden

Chemnitzer Str. 46a, D-01187 Dresden

GERMANY

Tel. +49 351 463 39884

Supplement S3 and S4. Comparison of selected correlation coefficients between online sports bettors with and without GD at initial and follow-up online survey

Table S3. Comparison of selected correlation coefficients between online sports bettors with and without GD at initial online survey.

Correlated variables	Coefficient without GD, <i>N</i>	Coefficient with GD, <i>N</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Sum number of bets / Alcohol use	-0.11* 470	-0.12 137	0.1	.918
Sum number of bets / Tobacco use	0.17* 468	-0.03 137	2.06	.04
Sum live stakes / Alcohol use	-0.09* 470	0.06 137	-1.53	.125
Standard deviation of odds / Tobacco use	0.1* 454	-0.03 134	1.31	.189
Sum amount of deposits / Alcohol use	-0.13* 470	0.05 137	-1.85	.065
Sum amount of deposits / Tobacco use	0.12* 468	-0.12 137	2.46	.014
Total stakes / Tobacco use	0.07 468	-0.22* 137	3	.003
Sum of prematch stakes / Tobacco use	0.08 468	-0.31* 137	4.09	< .001
Standard deviation of total stakes / Tobacco use	-0.09 454	-0.2* 134	1.13	.257

Note. GD = gambling disorder. Coefficients displayed are based on Spearman correlations. Asterisks indicate significance of the respective correlation on a $p < .05$ level as displayed in Tables 4 and 5 in the manuscript. For the calculation of standard deviations, a minimum number of at least one bet per considered month (i.e. a total of 6 or 12) is required. Alcohol and tobacco use are measured with a quantity-frequency-index (adapted from Gmel & Rehm, 2004). Depression, anxiety and somatization are measured with respective subscales of the Brief Symptoms Inventory-18 (Spitzer, 2011).

Table S4. Comparison of selected correlation coefficients between online sports bettors with and without GD at follow-up online survey.

Correlated variables	Coefficient without GD, <i>N</i>	Coefficient with GD, <i>N</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Sum number of bets / Alcohol use	-0.15* 249	-0.01 75	-1.05	.292
Sum number of bets / Tobacco use	0.17* 250	0.11 75	0.46	.648
Total stakes / Alcohol use	-0.17* 249	0.07 75	-1.8	.07
Sum of prematch stakes / Alcohol use	-0.16* 249	0.1 75	-1.95	.051
Sum live stakes / Alcohol use	-0.16* 249	0.05 75	-1.58	.115
Mean weighted odds / Tobacco use	0.16* 250	0.03 72	0.97	.335
Standard deviation of odds / Tobacco use	0.19* 243	0 68	1.38	.169
Sum amount of deposits / Alcohol use	-0.25* 249	0.08 75	-2.51	.012
Sum amount of withdrawals / Alcohol use	-0.15* 249	0.18 75	-2.49	.013

Sum number of bets / Depression	0.05 250	-0.26*	2.36	.018
Total stakes / Depression	0.05 250	-0.27*	2.44	.015
Total stakes / Somatization	0.01 250	-0.24*	1.9	.057
Sum of prematch stakes / Depression	0.07 250	-0.23*	2.27	.023
Sum of prematch stakes / Anxiety	0.08 250	-0.24*	2.43	.015
Sum of prematch stakes / Somatization	0 250	-0.25*	1.91	.057
Mean weighted odds / Depression	0.04 250	-0.26*	2.29	.022
Sum amount of deposits / Somatization	-0.01 250	-0.27*	1.99	.046
Sum amount of withdrawals / Anxiety	0.03 250	-0.23*	1.97	.049
Sum amount of withdrawals /	-0.01 250	-0.27*	1.99	.046

Note. GD = gambling disorder. Coefficients displayed are based on Spearman correlations. Asterisks indicate significance of the respective correlation on a $p < .05$ level as displayed in Tables 6 and 7 in the manuscript. For the calculation of standard deviations, a minimum number of at least one bet per considered month (i.e. a total of 6 or 12) is required. Alcohol and tobacco use are measured with a quantity-frequency-index (adapted from Gmel & Rehm, 2004). Depression, anxiety and somatization are measured with respective subscales of the Brief Symptoms Inventory-18 (Spitzer, 2011).

Please see the manuscript for details of the calculation of respective variables.